

COTTON LINT SEPARATION EQUIPMENT

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Abstract: After the ginning process, a short layer of fluff remains in the seed. The process of separating cotton wool from the seed is called linter, and the equipment that performs this process is called linter. The article talks about the construction of the main working bodies of Linter equipment and the process of separating fluff from seed.

Key words: Fiber, lint, technique, resource efficient, seed, technology, linter, energy.

Improving the cotton seed linting process is one of the main tasks of cotton ginning enterprises. One of the main working parts of a modern linter machine that affects the linting process is the adjuster. Its position and location in the working chamber relative to the saw cylinder is uniform along the length of the saw blade.

rotation, a certain pressure between the saw blades and saw cylinder and causes movement at speed.

PMP-160M, type 5LP and type 6LP linter equipment with UMPL working chamber are used for fluff separation, and fluff is separated from saw teeth using air. Linters also have a seed chamber bordered by a gin apron, a seed comb, a colosnik grid, and a top brush. Lintering of seeds is carried out in this chamber. The linting process is similar to the ginning process. From the working chamber of the linter to the rotating seed roller, it is processed by a saw cylinder. The difference between these processes is that in the saw gin, seeded cotton is processed, while in linters, ginned seeds are used. During the linter process, since the seed shaft cannot rotate under the action of the saw, in order to help it rotate, a counter-rotating device is installed in the chamber of the linters. The trimmer straightens the seed roller as it rotates, improving the arrival of hairier seeds on the saw teeth. The method of fluff separation in linters is based on the mechanical action of the saws on the rotating seed shaft, scraping the fluff from the surface of the seeds, then separating it from the saw tooth with the help of air and taking it to the condenser, where it is separated from the air. The main parameters of the linter are the amount of fluff separated from the seed and the productivity of the seed.

The working chamber of the machine has a great influence on the linting process. In modern 5LP linters, the linear speed of the saws in the saw cylinder

is 12.3 m/s, and the linear speed of the trimmer blades is 4.2 m/s. Based on this, it can be considered that the saw teeth affect the seed mass with a speed of 8.1 m/s. As a result of the impact of the saw on the seed at such a high speed and the impact of the trimmer on the seed roller, the seeds are damaged in the process of scraping the fluff from the surface of the seed. If the density of the seed bed is low, the adjusting blades cannot exert pressure on the seed. In this case, the effectiveness of fluff scraping decreases, and at the same time, the damage of the seed increases as a result of a lot of mechanical impact.

Figure 1. 5LP is a construction scheme of a branded linter and general Appearance.

Analytical analyzes of the working condition of the linters of the linter machines working in production, the influence on the linting process and the previous scientific and research works in this direction, the efficiency of the linter is improved when the number of blades in the linter is 4. , showed a positive effect on the linting process. At the same time, since the trimmer blades are made of metal and their linear speed is 4.2 m/sec, mechanical damage to the seeds was observed in the process of scraping the fluff from the seeds passing between the blades and the saw cylinder.

In the Linteming working chamber, the seeds falling into the chamber at the expense of the rotary trimmer and the saw cylinder form a rotary seed roller. With its teeth, the saw penetrates the seed shaft and hangs or scrapes off the fibrous mass on the surface of the seed - this is called lint. Fluff caught in the saw tooth is removed from the working chamber depending on the rotation of

the saw. In this case, the density of the seed bed is of great importance. Because the higher the density, the greater the amount of lint (percentage of fluff or sym) on the saw. As a result, linter productivity increases. The fiber attached to the saw teeth is transported through the colosnik gap and is separated from the saw teeth due to the speed of the air coming out of it when it reaches the air compartment. It separates the fluff and sends it down, that is, to the fluff-removing nozzle of the air chamber, and from there, the fluff goes to the condenser with air. The air coming out of the nozzle separates the fluff from the saw tooth, also separates the waste in the fluff due to the presence of the upper rake located there, and brings it down to the waste conveyor. The seeds, depending on the removal of fluff from their surface, (due to depilation) are separated from the seed shaft and fall to the surface of the colosnik and slide down to the seed conveyor and are taken to the next process.

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